

Thermodynamic Study of Metal(II)—Dopamine System in Aqueous Solution

PURUSHOTTAM B. CHAKRAWARTI*, B. L. VIJAYVARGIYA and H. N. SHARMA

Chemical Laboratories, M.V.M., Bhopal-462 002

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Stepwise stability constants and thermodynamic parameters, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been worked out for the reaction of dopamine with metal(II) ions in aqueous solution at 0, 25 and 37° and a fixed ionic strength of 0.1 M (KCl). Structures of the complexes isolated have been proposed on the basis of analytical data and ir spectra.

Utilising the results of this study, a mechanism for the pressor activity of adrenergic drugs has been proposed. Dopamine reacting with the enzyme, dopamine- β -oxidase, is converted into the pressor hormone norepinephrine. This reaction is supposed to be catalysed with the formation of an intermediate metal(II) ion bridged dopamine and the enzyme complex.

DOPAMINE (3,4-dihydroxyphenylethylamine) (1) is the immediate precursor in the biosynthesis of noradrenaline in the body. It increases blood pressure mainly by enhancing cardiac interaction. Peripheral resistance is not increased. The drug is being used experimentally for hypotension and shock.

Since the drug is of much medicinal value and is a good chelating agent with two phenolic hydroxy groups and one amino group, attempts have been made to study its complexes with some transition metals^{1,2}. However, no attempt has so far been made to investigate its reaction with metal(II) ions. In this communication, we report the results of our studies on the interaction of dopamine with metal(II) ions in aqueous solution and structures of the isolated chelates.

Experimental

All the chemical used were of high purity analytical grade. The sample of dopamine hydrochloride was obtained from Rhein (Germany). The preparation and standardisation of the ligand solution has been given earlier³, while the standardisation of the metal ion solutions and the other experimental details are the same as reported in case of metal(II)-noradrenaline system³.

Stoichiometry of the adducts formed was ascertained by conductometric and potentiometric

titrations. The stepwise and overall formation constants were calculated at three temperatures (0, 25 and 37°) and at a fixed ionic strength of 0.1 M (KCl), using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁴. It involved titration of the following thermostated mixtures of solutions with a 0.2 M alkali solution: (i) 5 ml of 0.02 M HCl solution, (ii) solution (i) +10 ml of 0.01 M dopamine solution, and (iii) solution (ii) +5 ml of 0.002 M metal ion solution. The ionic strength of the above solutions was maintained to 0.1 M by adding the required quantity of 1.0 M KCl solution, keeping the total volume at 50 ml with double-distilled water.

The values of $\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL^- were calculated using Irving Rossotti equations⁴. The values of the formation constants were directly obtained from the formation curves. The refined values for the same were computed by the best least-square fits (Table 1). The thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were calculated using the isotherm, the isobar and the Gibbs-Helmoltz's equations, respectively at 25 and 37° and ionic strength of 0.1 M with KCl (Table 2). The isolation of the metal adducts and their composition was ascertained by the methods described earlier³. The physical properties of the compounds isolated and their analytical data are given in Table 3 along with the important ir frequencies (recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer).

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometric studies based on conductometric (Fig. 1) and potentiometric (pH) titrations clearly indicate that metal(II) ions combine with one and two molecules of dopamine in stepwise manner. Further, pH titrations show liberation of only one proton during addition of each molecule

TABLE 1—STEPWISE FORMATION CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$\mu = 0.1 M (KCl)$				
Metal(II) ion	Temp. °C	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log B_2$
Be	0	8.40	5.20	13.60
	25	7.97	4.35	12.32
	37	7.25	4.30	11.55
Mg	0	5.00	2.85	7.85
	25	4.68	2.10	6.78
	37	4.80	1.80	6.10
Ca	0	4.50	2.00	6.50
	25	4.10	1.75	5.85
	37	4.00	1.60	5.60
Sr	0	3.72	1.52	5.24
	25	3.65	1.45	5.10
	37	3.50	1.25	4.75
Ba	0	3.45	1.30	4.75
	25	3.02	1.10	4.12
	37	2.92	1.00	3.92

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS AT 20°

$\mu = 0.1 M (KCl)$					
	BeII	MgII	CaII	SrII	BaII
$-\Delta G_1$	10.96	6.43	5.68	5.01	4.15
$-\Delta G_2$	5.97	2.89	2.40	2.00	1.50
$-\Delta G$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	16.58	8.84	7.52	6.83	5.41
$-\Delta H_1$	6.40	4.76	5.95	1.04	6.36
$-\Delta H_2$	19.65	3.72	3.72	1.04	2.98
$-\Delta H$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	19.65	6.85	9.23	5.80	7.44
$-\Delta S_1$	15.28	5.58	-1.09	13.32	-7.40
$-\Delta S_2$	-22.42	-2.81	-4.42	3.18	-4.92
$-\Delta S$ (cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-10.29	6.69	-5.72	1.75	-6.82

Fig. 1. Conductometric titrations of dopamine complexes.

of dopamine. Hence, the complexation of the two molecules of the ligand with metal(II) may be represented as

where, M is Be, Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba, and H_2L is $C_6H_3(OH)_2CH_2CHNH_2$. Formation of 1:1 and 1:2 (M-L) complexes was also indicated by the values of $\bar{n}$, which in no case exceeded 1.8.

An analysis of the formation curves (Fig. 2) clearly points out that addition of dopamine molecules to the metal ions is stepwise, i.e. one molecule of dopamine is first combined with one atom of the metal. The 1:1 complex thus formed did not appreciably combine with a second molecule of dopamine to give the 1:2 complex, until at least

 Fig. 2. Formation curves of M^{2+} -dopamine complexes at 25°: (1) Be, (2) Mg, (3) Ca, (4) Sr and (5) Ba.

70% of the 1:1 complex had been formed, i.e. the formation of the two species is independent of each other. This is similar to what has been reported for the amino acids⁵ and the other catecholamines^{6,7}.

A perusal of Tables 1 and 2 clearly indicates the standard sequence⁸ of stability for these complexes. Comparison of stability constant data with the corresponding adrenaline⁸ and noradrenaline⁹ systems suggests the order being, adrenaline > dopamine > noradrenaline, with Be^{II}, and adrenaline > noradrenaline > dopamine with rest of the metals used in this investigation.

A perusal of the values of the thermodynamic parameters (Table 2) shows clearly that the metal ions are enthalpy characterised and the values of ΔS , in addition to the high values of negative enthalpy change, are also negative. The high negative values of enthalpy change indicate considerable degree of covalence in metal to ligand bond. The negative values of entropy change is an indication

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL DATA AND IR BANDS (cm⁻¹)

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			$\nu_{\text{NH/OH}}$	$\delta_{\text{NH}}(\text{sec})$	$\nu_{\text{coord-H}_2\text{O}}$	δ_{OH}
		N	M	H ₂ O				
1.	Ligand	—	—	—	3 680m, 3 540m, 3 480w	1 660vw, 1 630m, 1 610m, 1 560w, 1 510vs, 890vs	—	1 355m, 1 330m, 1 270s, 1 030w
2.	Be(C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₂	8.79 (8.94)	2.83 (2.87)	—	3 620w, 3 470vs	1 660w, 1 630w, 1 610w, 1 560m, 1 515m	—	1 350s, 1 320m, 1 290s, 1 040s
3.	Mg(C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	7.59 (7.69)	6.57 (6.59)	9.82 (9.89)	3 640w, 3 520m, 3 480m, 3 340vs	1 660w, 1 630w, 1 580w, 830m	3 340vs, 3 210vs, 1 595m, 790m, 750m	1 325m, 1 280m, 1 060m
4.	Ca(C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	7.41 (7.37)	10.39 (10.52)	9.43 (9.47)	3 480–2 840b, 3 230vs	1 660vw, 1 630m, 1 660w, 825s	3 230vs, 1 610vs, 870w, 760w	1 380w, 1 345w, 1 270vw, 1 030m
5.	Sr(C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	6.39 (6.51)	20.20 (20.49)	8.37 (8.41)	3 580–3 040b, 3 480vs, 3 380vs, 3 290vs	1 660vw, 1 630m, 1 580w, 830s	4 386vs, 3 380vs, 1 610m, 880m, 760m	1 340m, 1 285m, 1 030w

All complexes are dark grey (except Sl. no. 5 which is light grey) crystalline, hygroscopic, decompose before melting, and soluble in water and alcohol.

of the decrease in the number of particles on complex formation.

The analytical data (Table 3) of the isolated adducts indicate the molecular formula to be M(HL)₂·2H₂O, which is similar to that obtained for the corresponding adrenaline⁶ and noradrenaline⁸ adducts. The ir spectral data (Table 3) of these complexes show considerable change in the characteristic frequencies of phenolic OH group, suggesting that the complexation might have taken place through the phenolic hydroxyl groups forming a five-membered ring as indicated by Andrews *et al.*⁷. Further, as the potentiometric (pH) titrations indicate liberation of only one proton in each step of addition of the ligand molecule, the following general structure (2) may be given to the isolated complexes.

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The presence of coordinated water is confirmed by the presence of bands at 3 600–3 200, 880 and 650 cm⁻¹.

The main factors involved in the maintenance of blood pressure are cardiac output and peripheral resistance, in addition to blood-volume, blood-viscosity and elasticity of the arterial walls. Dopamine is an adrenergic drug. It increases the blood pressure mainly by enhancing cardiac interaction. Peripheral resistance is not increased. Under hypotensive condition, adrenergic drugs acting on cell chemicals (specially with enzymes) of organs and

muscles innervated by sympathetic nerves release substances which elevate the blood pressure. Dopamine reacting with the enzyme dopamine- β -oxidase is converted into noradrenaline⁸, an active pressure hormone. The catalytic activity of the enzyme may be explained according to the following mechanism.

The enzyme, dopamine- β -oxidase has been shown to exist bound with the biologically active metal(II) ions (particularly Mg^{II}). M²⁺ ion has high coordination number, six. Hence, dopamines molecule form an intermediate, M²⁺ ion bridged mixed complex with the enzyme, which in turn is converted into noradrenaline. Formation of the intermediate complex may be visualised in the light of the results of the present investigation, which show that dopamine molecule acts as a bidentate ligand during chelation with M²⁺ ions resulting in formation of 1:1 and 1:2 (M—L) complexes. Thus maximum four coordination sites (out of six) of the M²⁺ ion are utilised and the remaining two positions (at least) are used in the M²⁺-enzyme bonding.

Further, as Wells⁹ has pointed out that the formation of a strain-free chelate ring may be involved in, or possibly even required for superior antihistaminic activity; hence the free energy of formation for the chelates involving a given metal ion could be used as an index of the effectiveness of the antihistamine. The results of the present investigation clearly indicate formation of a five membered chelate ring (structure 2), giving high values of free energy of formation (Table 2). This may be taken as an indication of the effectiveness of dopamine as a drug.

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